

Large-scale human celebrations increase global light pollution

Francisco Ramírez¹ |
Marta Coll¹

¹Institut de Ciències del Mar (ICM), CSIC, Barcelona, Spain; ²Facultat de Matemàtiques i Estadística, Universitat Politècnica de Catalunya BarcelonaTech (UPC), Barcelona, Spain; ³Remote Sensing and GIS Laboratory, Estación Biológica de Doñana (EBD), CSIC, Seville, Spain; ⁴Terrestrial Ecology Group (TEG-UAM), Department of Ecology, Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain; ⁵Centro de Investigación en Biodiversidad y Cambio Global (CIBC-UAM), Universidad Autónoma de Madrid, Madrid, Spain; ⁶Departamento de Ecología Evolutiva, Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales (MNCN), CSIC, Madrid, Spain; ⁷Centre for Science Communication, University of Otago, Dunedin, New Zealand; ⁸Conservation Department, Phillip Island Nature Parks, Cowes, Victoria, Australia and ⁹Departament de Fonaments Clínics, Bioestadística, Facultat de Medicina, Universitat de Barcelona (UB), Barcelona, Spain

Correspondence

Francisco Ramírez

Email: ramirez@icm.csic.es

Funding information

Spanish Government, Grant/Award Number: PID2021-124831OA-I00 and CEX2019-000928-S; Horizon Europe Program, Grant/Award Number: 101059877; Ramón y Cajal Programme, Grant/Award Number: RYC2020-030078-I; Ramón y Cajal Fellowship, Grant/Award Number: RYC2021-032656-I; UE «NextGenerationEU»/PRTR

Handling Editor: Ricardo Correia

Abstract

1. Culturally dependent human social behaviours involving artificial light usage can potentially affect light pollution patterns and thereby impact the night-time ecology in populated areas, although to date this has not been examined globally.
2. By analysing continuous (monthly), highly resolved, spatially explicit data on global night lights (Visible and Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite–Day/Night Band–VIIRS–DNB; 2014–2019) with circular statistical techniques, we evaluated whether macro-cultural activities involving social aggregations and the use of artificial lights shape annual lighting patterns globally.
3. Scheduled routines associated with cultural-specific festivities appear to be important drivers of observed seasonal patterns in urban night-time lights. For instance, the display of Christmas lights between Christmas and Epiphany Day celebrations (December–January) coincides with the annual peak in urban night-time light intensity in Christian countries. Analogously, night celebrations during the Holy Month of Ramadam (from May to July) or the month-long period of Karthika Masam (from October to November) fits with annual night light peaks in Muslim and Hindu countries. Annual peaks of urban light intensity in China and Vietnam also match with Chinese and Vietnamese (Tê't) New Year celebrations (January–February). In contrast, predominantly Buddhist countries, which do not have such prominent and prolonged celebrations involving artificial lights, show a relatively uniform distribution of night light peaks throughout the annual cycle.
4. Social behaviour and sociocultural contexts help explain how people modify the global nightscape and contribute to light pollution globally. Understanding the cultural contexts responsible for peaks in artificial light usage is an important first step if humans are to mitigate any deleterious effects associated with global increases in night-time light pollution.

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2023 The Authors. *People and Nature* published by John Wiley & Sons Ltd on behalf of British Ecological Society.

KEYWORDS

artificial lights at night, light pollution, social aggregations, VIIRS

1 | INTRODUCTION

Humans have profoundly altered Earth's ecosystems (Ripple et al., 2017; Vitousek et al., 1997). One of the most striking human fingerprints on Earth can be seen from space; that is, the transformation of the nightscape by the increase in light levels associated with the use of artificial lights: so-called light pollution (Falchi et al., 2016; Kyba et al., 2017). Artificial light intensity and the lit surface of the Earth have increased dramatically over the last decade (Kyba et al., 2017, 2023; Sánchez de Miguel et al., 2021). This trend is likely to accelerate in the future as manufactured light sources continue to gain efficiency and lowered costs of production and usage, resulting in greater use of lights (Kyba et al., 2014, 2017; Sánchez de Miguel, Bennie, et al., 2022). Despite night-time light pollution being recognized as a global change phenomenon with consequences that go well beyond urban areas (Gaston et al., 2021; Luginbuhl et al., 2014), it is widely ignored in public and private policymaking in comparison to other forms of human-based pollution (Davies & Smyth, 2018; Gaston et al., 2021; Kyba et al., 2014).

Deleterious effects of light pollution have been reported at multiple levels: from individuals, to communities and ecosystem functioning (Gaston et al., 2013; Hölker, Wolter, et al., 2010; Kyba & Hölker, 2013; Rodríguez et al., 2017; Sanders & Gaston, 2018), affecting a vast array of life: from microbes to mammals, including humans (Gaston et al., 2013). Light pollution effects have been also recorded in both terrestrial and marine realms (Gaston & Sánchez de Miguel, 2022; Marangoni et al., 2022), including key biodiversity areas (Garrett et al., 2019). However, global patterns of light pollution are unevenly distributed in time and space (Falchi et al., 2016; Hölker, Moss, et al., 2010; Kyba et al., 2017; Levin et al., 2020; Román & Stokes, 2015) and it is important to ascertain the reasons for this to ascribe both the potential impacts of light pollution and any possible means of mitigation.

Patterns in light pollution have typically been associated with socioeconomic factors, such as gross domestic product, with wealthier countries producing more light than lower-income countries (Levin et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2014). However, the use of lights is also a well-recognized phenomenon associated with macro-cultural activities involving human aggregations, (Ciftci et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Ma, 2019; Román & Stokes, 2015; Zhang et al., 2020). Increases in urban night-time light pollution has been previously linked to particular festivities involving the use of artificial lights (Liu et al., 2019; Román & Stokes, 2015; Sánchez de Miguel, Zamorano, et al., 2022), yet no previous studies have evaluated how such country-specific sociocultural contexts affect annual lighting patterns globally.

In this study, we used a continuous time series of satellite imagery showing monthly night-time light radiance to estimate the proportion of pixels in urban areas associated with night light peaks for every month covered by our study. These proportions were used

as a proxy for the relative extent of the lighted area per month. Cultural-specific seasonal lighting patterns throughout a 12-month cycle were then assessed using circular statistical techniques. We hypothesized that cultural contexts and country-specific celebrations involving large human aggregations and the use of artificial lights would shape spatial and temporal patterns of light intensity throughout the annual cycle. Understanding such cultural contexts responsible for peaks in artificial light usage is an important prerequisite to mitigate any deleterious effects associated with the global increase in night-time light pollution.

2 | METHODS

Monthly data on night lights (radiance, nanoWatts/cm²/sr) were extracted from Visible and Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite–Day/Night Band (VIIRS-DNB) sensors on board the Suomi satellite. This data source provides global monthly night-time light data at 0.00042° horizontal resolution (ca. 500 m/pixel resolution at middle latitudes) and is provided by the Earth Observation Group, Payne Institute for Public Policy, Colorado School of Mines (<https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/>; publicly available on Google Earth Engine–GEE). The time series used here spanned the period from 2014 to 2019. More recent data were not considered in the analyses to avoid any abnormal effects of the COVID-19 pandemic on night-time light patterns (Bustamante-Calabria et al., 2021; Jechow & Hölker, 2020).

To consider only urban areas, where most human celebrations take place, night light data were first masked by Global Human Settlement Layers (GHSL), Built-Up Grid 1975–1990–2000–2015 (P2016), based on Landsat images also available in GEE. Visual inspection of GHSL, in comparison with highly resolved satellite images from GEE, suggested that the GHSL tended to overestimate urban areas, hence, filtering of the urban regions was further improved by selecting only those pixels with a median night light radiance >2 nanoWatts/cm²/sr.

For every single pixel within urban areas, we identified the month at which night lights peak annually and calculated the extent of lighted regions per country (i.e. the proportion of urban pixels in which night lights peak for a particular month). This makes comparable all urban pixels around the globe, regardless of the absolute radiances and the data product used (e.g. VIIRS-VNP46A2, <https://doi.org/10.5067/VIIRS/VNP46A2.001>; see Figures S1 and S2 and Data Sources list in Supporting Information), while overcoming calibration issues associated with VIIRS-DNB. Social customs and macro-cultural, scheduled festivities are mainly associated with specific religious traditions. To reduce variability ascribed to ethnically and culturally diverse countries, we considered those countries ($n=105$) where more than 70% of their population adhered to one of the world's four religions to which nearly 80% of the world's

8 billion human population is affiliated: Christianity (32% world's population), Islam (24.1%), Hinduism (15.1%) and Buddhism (6.9%; Hackett et al., 2017). Information on religions were obtained from: <https://www.arcgis.com/home/item.html?id=515a2320d91e40ef9f9d96708c65fd14> (ESRI Canada Education Team). As one of the largest and most densely populated regions in the world, we also included China and Vietnam in our analyses. In these countries, most people are not affiliated with any of the above-mentioned religions. However, certain traditions such as the Chinese and the Vietnamese (Tê't) New Year also involve large human movements and aggregations that include the use of artificial lights (Ma, 2019).

Given the whole-year circular nature of our data, we evaluated seasonal patterns in night-time light peaks through circular statistics. First, we used our proxy for the relative extent of lighted areas per month to identify the months at which yearly peaks in lighted areas occurred ('scorepeak' R library) (Ochi, 2019). Rayleigh tests were then used for testing against uniformity in the distribution of these peaks when unimodality was suspected, while a Kuiper test was

used for the cases of possible bimodality or multimodality (Landler et al., 2018); for both Rayleigh and Kuiper tests, p -values were obtained via Monte Carlo's simulation with 99 iterations in each case.

3 | RESULTS

We found that global night-time light patterns were nonuniformly distributed seasonally in Christian (Rayleigh test=0.38, p -value=0.01), Muslim (Kuiper test=3.87, p -value=0.03) and Hindu (Rayleigh test=0.364, p -value=0.01) countries, as well as in China and Vietnam (Kuiper test=2.77, p -value <0.01; Figure 1). Only Buddhist countries showed a relatively uniform distribution of night lights peaks throughout the annual cycle (Figure 1; Rayleigh test=0.152, p -value=0.79).

Overall, urban night light intensity peaked during massive celebrations. In countries with a mainly Christian tradition, urban night-time light intensity peaked during December–January, matching the period

FIGURE 1 Night light monthly patterns per country and major cultural contexts. (a) Cultural contexts for countries included in the analyses. We considered countries with more than 70% of the population adhering to a specific religion, as well as China and Vietnam, where large and scheduled human aggregations are associated with New Year celebrations. White-coloured countries (NA) were not considered. (b) Mean annual peak in night light per country. (c) Circular tests and statistics for seasonal patterns in night light for the countries grouped according to their major cultural contexts.

between Christmas and Epiphany Day celebrations. This was particularly true for high-income countries in the Northern Hemisphere (Figure 1). Night light peaks also differed among Christian countries off the Northern Hemisphere, with night light intensity peaks spanning from December to January in those countries that celebrate Christmas on 25 December; and peaking in January in Orthodox Christian countries off Eastern Europe that celebrate Christmas on or about 7 January (Figure 1). In countries with a Muslim tradition, the night light peaks occurred mostly during May, June and July, coinciding with the Holy Month of Ramadan, particularly in the Middle East and North Africa (Figure 1). During the study period, depending upon the year, Ramadan took place in May, June or July, with the seasonal patterns in night light closely tracking these interannual changes (Figure 2). Night-time light peaks in Hindu countries are concentrated in October–November (Figure 1), matching festivities associated with Diwali. In China and Vietnam, night light peaks mainly span from January to February, thus matching with the Chinese New Year, and the Têt celebrations (Figure 1). These celebrations follow the lunisolar calendar and, hence, alternated between January and February during the study period, depending upon the year. Annual night light peaks in urban areas within these countries closely track these interannual changes (Figure 3).

4 | DISCUSSION

Culturally driven, human aggregations and scheduled routines shape local to regional patterns of night light pollution (Liu et al., 2019;

Román & Stokes, 2015; Sánchez de Miguel, Zamorano, et al., 2022). Here, we show for the first time that global night-time light pollution peaks concurrently with macro-cultural, country-specific festivities involving large human aggregations and the use of human-made artificial lights as part of those festivities. This link between the usage of lights and human festivities needs to be considered when determining how people modify the global nightscape and how to mitigate any deleterious effects associated with the effects of light pollution levels.

4.1 | Confounding measurements of festivities and night-time light patterns

Measurements of night light intensity vary as a function of the lunar phase, albedo changes, cloud coverage and sensor viewing geometry (Kyba et al., 2011; Levin et al., 2020; Li et al., 2019; Liu et al., 2019). In addition, VIIRS-DNB system collects imagery after midnight (around 1:30 a.m.): that is, after the peak lighting that occurs in the early part of the evening (Elvidge et al., 2013). Also, the greater blue emissions (380–450 nm) associated with the recent transition from sodium-vapour lamps to broad white light-emitting diodes (LEDs) are largely overlooked as VIIRS-DNB is sensitive from 480 to 920 nm (Kyba et al., 2017; Levin et al., 2020; Sánchez de Miguel, Bennie, et al., 2022). Finally, ethnical and cultural diversity can result in contrasting spatial-temporal patterns in night-time light intensity at a subnational level (Ciftci et al., 2021).

Despite all these confounding factors that might obscure patterns of artificial light usage, our results point unequivocally to

FIGURE 2 Night light seasonal patterns for Muslim countries from the Middle East and North Africa, closely tracking interannual changes during Ramadan.

FIGURE 3 Night light seasonal patterns for China and Vietnam, closely tracking interannual changes during New Year celebrations.

the use of decorative lighting for festivals or increased evening/night-time activity during major festivities being important drivers of global patterns in artificial night lighting. Gregarious human behaviours associated with scheduled festivities and religious or civil holidays, then affect the year-round night light patterns (Liu et al., 2019; Ma, 2019; Román & Stokes, 2015). The observed night light intensity peaks point to the influence that massive social festivals involving the use of artificial lights during Christmas, Ramadan, Diwali and the New Year celebrations of China and Vietnam can have as main drivers of global annual night light patterns. In contrast, we did not observe a well-defined night light peak for Buddhist countries. Vesak is the most important Buddhist celebration in South and Southeast Asia. It occurs in May but only on a single day and, while it can involve the use of candles, butter lamps and lanterns (Vesak kudu), their intensity and duration are unlikely to be enough to significantly alter monthly patterns of artificial light production in Buddhist countries.

In Christian countries, urban night-time light intensity peaks during December–January, thus matching the period between Christmas and Epiphany Day celebrations. For Northern Hemisphere countries in high latitudes, such seasonal patterns of artificial night-time light levels could also be affected by seasonal changes in albedo related to vegetation and snow cover (Levin et al., 2020). However, we observed this same pattern of increased light production from December to January in Christian countries at middle and low latitudes in the Northern Hemisphere, confirming that the display of Christmas lights is the most likely producer of the additional light pollution observed in Christian countries during this period irrespective of any effects of albedo (Román & Stokes, 2015; Sánchez de

Miguel, Zamorano, et al., 2022). Further support for this is provided by comparing seasonal night-time light patterns between Christian countries and Orthodox Christian countries off Eastern Europe, as observed night light intensity peaks matched the exact periods when they celebrate Christmas.

In Muslim countries, spatial–temporal night light patterns may vary according to the spatial distribution of different Islamic sects such as Shia and Sunni (Liu et al., 2019; Figure S3) and the different national and subnational levels of religiosity (Ciftci et al., 2021). Even so, our results reveal that night light peaks occur during the Holy Month of Ramadan, when prayer and eating shift later into the night, causing increased usage of artificial lights (Figure 1). This is particularly true for nations in the Middle East and North Africa. As the Ramadan period varies between years, we were able to test whether changes in the dates of this major period of festivity were mirrored by changes in night-time light patterns (Ciftci et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2019; Román & Stokes, 2015). We showed that seasonal patterns in night light intensity closely track interannual changes of Ramadan dates; thus, supporting our hypothesis that social aggregations at night associated with cultural festivities enhance light pollution levels (Figure 2).

Similarly, the night-time light peaks we observed in Hindu countries, which are concentrated in October–November (Figure 1), match celebrations associated with Diwali, one of the biggest Hindu festivals whereby people light up their houses during the night for the month-long period of Karthika Masam (Ravindra et al., 2022).

Muslim and Hindu countries that are found in North Africa, the Middle East and South Asia are not affected by seasonal changes

in albedo. This helps confirm that seasonal patterns of night-time lights in urban areas result mostly from human behaviour and scheduled routines associated with religious festivities that involve artificial lights rather than any annual environmental changes affecting albedo.

Chinese New Year, and Têt celebrations in Vietnam, are among the most important holidays in East Asia. They take place in January–February, matching annual peaks in urban night-time light intensity. In addition to the use of artificial lights to decorate urban areas, these festivities involve massive human migrations from densely populated areas in big cities to people's hometowns for family reunion dinners. This can involve redistributing light pollution spatially, and the expansion of the lit surface (Ma, 2019).

4.2 | North versus south

Contrasting night-time light patterns were observed between both hemispheres. The match between religious and country-specific festivities and annual night-time light peaks is particularly apparent in the Northern Hemisphere, while this relationship fades in the Southern Hemisphere. This pattern points to other potential drivers of seasonal patterns in urban night-time lights. For instance, increases in street lighting and in cloud coverage during the winter in the Northern Hemisphere may partially explain these contrasting patterns (Elvidge et al., 2017; Kyba et al., 2011). The socioeconomic context may also contribute to explain such differences, as wealthier Christian countries in North America and Europe typically produce more light (Levin et al., 2020; Shi et al., 2014); and may invest more economic resources to decorate their streets with brighter Christmas lights. Accordingly, the Christmas peak in night-time light intensity observed for the northern and wealthier Christian faith countries is less pronounced than in the mainly economically constrained countries of the Southern Hemisphere (Figure 1). Economic factors may also affect the duration of lighting, with night-time lighting in wealthier countries from the Northern Hemisphere persisting longer between dusk and dawn (Gaston et al., 2012).

Other nonreligious festivities and activities driving scheduled human routines, such as civil holidays, could also play a role in shaping seasonal patterns of night light intensity, potentially masking the effect of religious festivities (Liu et al., 2019; Ma, 2019; Román & Stokes, 2015, see also Figures S1 and S2). Differences in albedo related to vegetation and snow cover may also contribute to the apparent mismatch between religious festivities and the annual night light for some countries in the Southern Hemisphere (Levin et al., 2020).

4.3 | Implications for global light pollution

Artificial lighting has dramatically increased over recent decades (Kyba et al., 2017, 2023). The cultural contexts addressed in this study help explain how people modify the global nightscape, with

implications for global night light pollution and far-reaching impacts on natural ecosystems.

The increasing global trend in the lit surface of the Earth has been previously related to levels of both gross domestic product and human population density, suggesting that trends and patterns of light pollution will only worsen with continued economic development and growth in the human population (Garrett et al., 2019). Deleterious effects of night light pollution are not only driven by direct emissions from the source of night-time lighting in urban areas, but also by upwardly emitted or reflected artificial light being scattered in the atmosphere by water, dust and gas molecules: the artificial skyglow that extends over about 23% of the global land area (Falchi et al., 2016). As a consequence, light pollution may reach natural systems far beyond urban areas (Gaston et al., 2012, 2021). Indeed, recent estimates suggest that less than a third of the world's Key Biodiversity Areas have completely pristine night-time skies (Garrett et al., 2019). The Mediterranean and temperate ecosystems are those experiencing the most significant increases in exposure to artificial light at night (Bennie et al., 2015).

Biological impacts of light pollution include changes in physiology, behaviour and overall functioning at individual and community levels (Da Silva et al., 2015; Grubisic et al., 2019; Sanders & Gaston, 2018). Even weak and temporary artificial light can disturb organisms adapted to natural levels and cycles of light (Aulsebrook et al., 2022). Effective mitigation of these pervasive effects would require reductions in outdoor artificial lighting levels in places where it is used by people (Garrett et al., 2019). Other mitigation measures could include limiting the duration and the area of lighting or changing its intensity and spectrum (Gaston et al., 2012; Figure S3).

Our findings also highlight the need for global policies directed towards the sustainable use of artificial lights to reduce or limit the outputs of artificial lights used in association with social festivities, thereby helping to minimize the harmful effects of increasing light pollution on the Earth's ecosystem. For instance, the use of blue-rich light sources may produce more skyglow than an equivalent intensity of yellow-rich lighting (Falchi et al., 2011). Furthermore, blue-rich light is more detrimental for organisms (Davies et al., 2013; Longcore et al., 2018). Reducing the trespass of light from light displays associated with religious festivities by using different wavelengths and/or seminatural barriers to artificial light may also help mitigate the ecological impacts of such light pollution (Gaston et al., 2012; Figure S3).

Light pollution, and its pervasive consequences, is a nascent research field (Davies & Smyth, 2018). However, the results from this study and our existing knowledge base are already sufficient to justify planning management actions to reduce light pollution and mitigate deleterious effects (Kyba & Höfker, 2013; Levin et al., 2020; Lyytimäki, 2015), including those super-polluter events associated with major sociocultural activities such as religious festivities.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Francisco Ramírez, Airam Rodríguez, Marta Coll, Andre Chiaradia and Josep L. Carrasco conceived the work. Diego García, Yago Cordon, Francisco Ramírez and Josep L. Carrasco extracted and analysed the

data. Francisco Ramírez, Airam Rodríguez and Lloyd S. Davis drafted the paper. All authors contributed substantially to the interpretation of results, and the writing, reviewing and editing of the work.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We thank Maria Bas for her valuable help with graphic editing. We also thank Ricardo Correia, Alejandro Sánchez de Miguel and one anonymous reviewer for their comments on an earlier draft. The authors do not discriminate as to nationality, race, religious beliefs, class or political opinions.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The authors acknowledge the Spanish Government through the 'Severo Ochoa Centre of Excellence' accreditation (CEX2019-000928-S, hereafter SO), and the grant agreement PID2021-124831OA-I00 (SOSPEN). The work is also supported by GES4SEAS project, funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe Program (grant agreement no. 101059877). F.R. was supported by SO and by the Ramón y Cajal Programme (Spanish Ministerio de Ciencia e Innovación, RYC2020-030078-I). A.R. was contracted by a Ramón y Cajal Fellowship (RYC2021-032656-I) funded by MCIN/AEI/10.13039/501100011033 and the UE «NextGenerationEU»/PRTR.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

The authors declare no competing interests.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Datasets are publicly available on Google Earth Engine (<https://earthengine.google.com/>). VIIRS sensor products are provided by the Earth Observation Group, Payne Institute for Public Policy, Colorado School of Mines (<https://eogdata.mines.edu/products/vnl/>). Methods and procedures used in this study are available at <https://github.com/Digdgeo/ReligionsLights>.

ORCID

Francisco Ramírez <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9670-486X>

Diego García <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2757-7112>

Airam Rodríguez <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-7882-135X>

Marta Coll <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6235-5868>

Lloyd S. Davis <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1131-7647>

Andre Chiaradia <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6178-4211>

Josep L. Carrasco <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1184-0753>

REFERENCES

- Aulsebrook, A. E., Jechow, A., Krop-Benesch, A., Kyba, C. C. M., Longcore, T., Perkin, E. K., & van Grunsven, R. H. A. (2022). Nocturnal lighting in animal research should be replicable and reflect relevant ecological conditions. *Biology Letters*, 18(3), 20220035. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsbl.2022.0035>
- Bennie, J., Duffy, J., Davies, T., Correa-Cano, M., & Gaston, K. (2015). Global trends in exposure to light pollution in natural terrestrial ecosystems. *Remote Sensing*, 7(3), 2715–2730. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs70302715>
- Bustamante-Calabria, M., Sánchez de Miguel, A., Martín-Ruiz, S., Ortiz, J.-L., Vilchez, J. M., Pelegrina, A., García, A., Zamorano, J., Bennie, J., & Gaston, K. J. (2021). Effects of the COVID-19 lockdown on urban light emissions: Ground and satellite comparison. *Remote Sensing*, 13(2), Article 2. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13020258>
- Ciftci, S., Robbins, M., & Zaytseva, S. (2021). Devotion at sub-national level: Ramadan, nighttime lights, and religiosity in the Egyptian Governorates. *International Journal of Public Opinion Research*, 33(1), 99–117. <https://doi.org/10.1093/ijpor/edaa019>
- Da Silva, A., Valcu, M., & Kempenaers, B. (2015). Light pollution alters the phenology of dawn and dusk singing in common European songbirds. *Philosophical Transactions of the Royal Society B: Biological Sciences*, 370(1667), 20140126. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rstb.2014.0126>
- Davies, T. W., Bennie, J., Inger, R., de Ibarra, N. H., & Gaston, K. J. (2013). Artificial light pollution: Are shifting spectral signatures changing the balance of species interactions? *Global Change Biology*, 19(5), 1417–1423. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.12166>
- Davies, T. W., & Smyth, T. (2018). Why artificial light at night should be a focus for global change research in the 21st century. *Global Change Biology*, 24(3), 872–882. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.13927>
- Elvidge, C. D., Baugh, K., Zhizhin, M., & Hsu, F. C. (2013). Why VIIRS data are superior to DMSP for mapping nighttime lights. *Proceedings of the Asia-Pacific Advanced Network*, 35, 62–69. <https://doi.org/10.7125/APAN.35.7>
- Elvidge, C. D., Baugh, K., Zhizhin, M., Hsu, F. C., & Ghosh, T. (2017). VIIRS night-time lights. *International Journal of Remote Sensing*, 38(21), 5860–5879. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01431161.2017.1342050>
- Falchi, F., Cinzano, P., Duriscoe, D., Kyba, C. C. M., Elvidge, C. D., Baugh, K., Portnov, B. A., Rybnikova, N. A., & Furgoni, R. (2016). The new world atlas of artificial night sky brightness. *Science Advances*, 2(6), e1600377. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1600377>
- Falchi, F., Cinzano, P., Elvidge, C. D., Keith, D. M., & Haim, A. (2011). Limiting the impact of light pollution on human health, environment and stellar visibility. *Journal of Environmental Management*, 92(10), 2714–2722. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jenvman.2011.06.029>
- Garrett, J. K., Donald, P. F., & Gaston, K. J. (2019). Skyglow extends into the world's key biodiversity areas. *Animal Conservation*, 23, 153–159. <https://doi.org/10.1111/acv.12480>
- Gaston, K. J., Ackermann, S., Bennie, J., Cox, D. T. C., Phillips, B. B., Sánchez de Miguel, A., & Sanders, D. (2021). Pervasiveness of biological impacts of artificial light at night. *Integrative and Comparative Biology*, 61(3), 1098–1110. <https://doi.org/10.1093/icb/ibab145>
- Gaston, K. J., Bennie, J., Davies, T. W., & Hopkins, J. (2013). The ecological impacts of nighttime light pollution: A mechanistic appraisal: Nighttime light pollution. *Biological Reviews*, 88(4), 912–927. <https://doi.org/10.1111/brv.12036>
- Gaston, K. J., Davies, T. W., Bennie, J., & Hopkins, J. (2012). REVIEW: Reducing the ecological consequences of night-time light pollution: Options and developments. *Journal of Applied Ecology*, 49(6), 1256–1266. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1365-2664.2012.02212.x>
- Gaston, K. J., & Sánchez de Miguel, A. (2022). Environmental impacts of artificial light at night. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources*, 47(1), 373–398. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-environ-112420-014438>
- Grubisic, M., Haim, A., Bhusal, P., Dominoni, D. M., Gabriel, K. M. A., Jechow, A., Kupprat, F., Lerner, A., Marchant, P., Riley, W., Stebelova, K., van Grunsven, R. H. A., Zeman, M., Zubidat, A. E., & Hölker, F. (2019). Light pollution, circadian photoreception, and melatonin in vertebrates. *Sustainability*, 11(22), Article 22. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11226400>
- Hackett, C., Cooperman, A., & Schiller, A. (2017). *Babies born to Muslims will begin to outnumber Christian births by 2035; people with no religion face a birth dearth*. Pew Research Center.

- Hölker, F., Moss, T., Griefahn, B., Kloas, W., Voigt, C. C., Henckel, D., Hänel, A., Kappeler, P. M., Völker, S., Schwöpe, A., Franke, S., Uhrlandt, D., Fischer, J., Klenke, R., Wolter, C., & Tockner, K. (2010). The dark side of light: A transdisciplinary research agenda for light pollution policy. *Ecology and Society*, 15(4), art13. <https://doi.org/10.5751/ES-03685-150413>
- Hölker, F., Wolter, C., Perkin, E. K., & Tockner, K. (2010). Light pollution as a biodiversity threat. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 25(12), 681–682. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2010.09.007>
- Jechow, A., & Hölker, F. (2020). Evidence that reduced air and road traffic decreased artificial night-time skyglow during COVID-19 lockdown in Berlin, Germany. *Remote Sensing*, 12(20), Article 20. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12203412>
- Kyba, C. C. M., Altıntaş, Y. Ö., Walker, C. E., & Newhouse, M. (2023). Citizen scientists report global rapid reductions in the visibility of stars from 2011 to 2022. *Science*, 379(6629), 265–268. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.abq7781>
- Kyba, C. C. M., Hänel, A., & Hölker, F. (2014). Redefining efficiency for outdoor lighting. *Energy & Environmental Science*, 7(6), 1806–1809. <https://doi.org/10.1039/C4EE00566J>
- Kyba, C. C. M., & Hölker, F. (2013). Do artificially illuminated skies affect biodiversity in nocturnal landscapes? *Landscape Ecology*, 28(9), 1637–1640. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10980-013-9936-3>
- Kyba, C. C. M., Kuester, T., Sánchez de Miguel, A., Baugh, K., Jechow, A., Hölker, F., Bennie, J., Elvidge, C. D., Gaston, K. J., & Guanter, L. (2017). Artificially lit surface of earth at night increasing in radiance and extent. *Science Advances*, 3(11), e1701528. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.1701528>
- Kyba, C. C. M., Ruhtz, T., Fischer, J., & Hölker, F. (2011). Cloud coverage acts as an amplifier for ecological light pollution in urban ecosystems. *PLoS ONE*, 6(3), e17307. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pone.0017307>
- Landler, L., Ruxton, G. D., & Malkemper, E. P. (2018). Circular data in biology: Advice for effectively implementing statistical procedures. *Behavioral Ecology and Sociobiology*, 72(8), 128. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00265-018-2538-y>
- Levin, N., Kyba, C. C. M., Zhang, Q., Sánchez de Miguel, A., Román, M. O., Li, X., Portnov, B. A., Molthan, A. L., Jechow, A., Miller, S. D., Wang, Z., Shrestha, R. M., & Elvidge, C. D. (2020). Remote sensing of night lights: A review and an outlook for the future. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 237, 111443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111443>
- Li, X., Ma, R., Zhang, Q., Li, D., Liu, S., He, T., & Zhao, L. (2019). Anisotropic characteristic of artificial light at night—Systematic investigation with VIIRS DNB multi-temporal observations. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 233, 111357. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.rse.2019.111357>
- Liu, S., Li, X., Levin, N., & Jendryke, M. (2019). Tracing cultural festival patterns using time-series of VIIRS monthly products. *Remote Sensing Letters*, 10(12), 1172–1181. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2150704X.2019.1666313>
- Longcore, T., Rodríguez, A., Witherington, B., Penniman, J. F., Herf, L., & Herf, M. (2018). Rapid assessment of lamp spectrum to quantify ecological effects of light at night. *Journal of Experimental Zoology Part A: Ecological and Integrative Physiology*, 329(8–9), 511–521. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jez.2184>
- Luginbuhl, C. B., Boley, P. A., & Davis, D. R. (2014). The impact of light source spectral power distribution on sky glow. *Journal of Quantitative Spectroscopy and Radiative Transfer*, 139, 21–26. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2013.12.004>
- Lyytimäki, J. (2015). Avoiding overly bright future: The systems intelligence perspective on the management of light pollution. *Environmental Development*, 16, 4–14. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.envdev.2015.06.009>
- Ma, T. (2019). Quantitative responses of satellite-derived night-time light signals to urban depopulation during Chinese New Year. *Remote Sensing Letters*, 10(2), 139–148. <https://doi.org/10.1080/2150704X.2018.1530484>
- Marangoni, L. F. B., Davies, T., Smyth, T., Rodríguez, A., Hamann, M., Duarte, C., Pendoley, K., Berge, J., Maggi, E., & Levy, O. (2022, February). Impacts of artificial light at night in marine ecosystems—A review. *Global Change Biology*, 28, 5346–5367. <https://doi.org/10.1111/gcb.16264>
- Ochi, S. (2019). *scorepeak: Peak functions for peak detection in univariate time series* (0.1.2). <https://CRAN.R-project.org/package=scorepeak>
- Ravindra, K., Kumar, S., & Mor, S. (2022). Long term assessment of firework emissions and air quality during Diwali festival and impact of 2020 fireworks ban on air quality over the states of Indo Gangetic Plains airshed in India. *Atmospheric Environment*, 285, 119223. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.atmosenv.2022.119223>
- Ripple, W. J., Wolf, C., Newsome, T. M., Galetti, M., Alamgir, M., Crist, E., Mahmoud, M. I., & Laurance, W. F. (2017). World scientists' warning to humanity: A second notice. *Bioscience*, 67(12), 1026–1028. <https://doi.org/10.1093/biosci/bix125>
- Rodríguez, A., Holmes, N. D., Ryan, P. G., Wilson, K.-J., Faulquier, L., Murillo, Y., Raine, A. F., Penniman, J. F., Neves, V., Rodríguez, B., Negro, J. J., Chiaradia, A., Dann, P., Anderson, T., Metzger, B., Shirai, M., Deppe, L., Wheeler, J., Hodum, P., ... Corre, M. L. (2017). Seabird mortality induced by land-based artificial lights: Seabird mortality and artificial lights. *Conservation Biology*, 31(5), 986–1001. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cobi.12900>
- Román, M. O., & Stokes, E. C. (2015). Holidays in lights: Tracking cultural patterns in demand for energy services. *Earth's Future*, 3(6), 182–205. <https://doi.org/10.1002/2014EF000285>
- Sánchez de Miguel, A., Bennie, J., Rosenfeld, E., Dzurjak, S., & Gaston, K. J. (2021). First estimation of global trends in nocturnal power emissions reveals acceleration of light pollution. *Remote Sensing*, 13(16), Article 16. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs13163311>
- Sánchez de Miguel, A., Bennie, J., Rosenfeld, E., Dzurjak, S., & Gaston, K. J. (2022). Environmental risks from artificial nighttime lighting widespread and increasing across Europe. *Science Advances*, 8(37), eabl6891. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abl6891>
- Sánchez de Miguel, A., Zamorano, J., Gallego, J., Montes, D., & Almazan, M. (2022). The light pollution generated by Christmas lighting in Madrid is less than that produced by sports fields. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5939657>
- Sanders, D., & Gaston, K. J. (2018). How ecological communities respond to artificial light at night. *Journal of Experimental Zoology Part A: Ecological and Integrative Physiology*, 329, 394–400. <https://doi.org/10.1002/jez.2157>
- Shi, K., Yu, B., Huang, Y., Hu, Y., Yin, B., Chen, Z., Chen, L., & Wu, J. (2014). Evaluating the ability of NPP-VIIRS nighttime light data to estimate the gross domestic product and the electric power consumption of China at multiple scales: A comparison with DMSP-OLS data. *Remote Sensing*, 6(2), 1705–1724. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs6021705>
- Vitousek, P. M., Mooney, H. A., Lubchenco, J., & Melillo, J. M. (1997). Human domination of earth's ecosystems. *Science*, 277(5325), 494–499. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.277.5325.494>
- Zhang, C., Pei, Y., Li, J., Qin, Q., & Yue, J. (2020). Application of Luojia 1-01 nighttime images for detecting the light changes for the 2019 spring festival in Western Cities, China. *Remote Sensing*, 12(9), 1416. <https://doi.org/10.3390/rs12091416>

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Additional supporting information can be found online in the Supporting Information section at the end of this article.

Figure S1. Night light seasonal patterns associated to 'La Feria de Abril' (https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Seville_Fair).

Figure S2. Comparison of average radiance trends in two areas of Seville city, Spain, by using two products from the Day/Night Band of the Visible Infrared Imaging Radiometer Suite instrument (VIIRS DNB).

Figure S3. Nocturnal landscape of Kuala Lumpur, Malaysia, during Eid al-Fit, the Muslim festival marking the end of the fast of Ramadan, on 17 July 2015. At the bottom right corner, streets with white- and blue-rich lights where celebrations are taking place. Photo by Airam Rodríguez.

How to cite this article: Ramírez, F., Cordon, Y., García, D., Rodríguez, A., Coll, M., Davis, L. S., Chiaradia, A., & Carrasco, J. L. (2023). Large-scale human celebrations increase global light pollution. *People and Nature*, 00, 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1002/pan3.10520>